

Hope action theory: An intervention career development for adolescence

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Abstract

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and the development of technological disruption in the current era of globalization have resulted in uncertainty and challenges, especially in the field of workforce recruitment. This condition requires readiness for career selection in the pre-employment age profile. Therefore, effective career guidance is increasingly needed. This study aimed to map the HAI (Hope-Action Inventory) profile of 82 high school students as the basis for career guidance and counseling service programs in high school. The method used in this research was a descriptive study of hope-action competencies assessment. The measurement of HAI competencies was important for effectively managing one's career development. This study found that 13% of students were still in the low expected action competence category. Several dimensions of competence measured showed a range of several dimensions of hope-action competence that were still undetermined, namely the dimensions of self-clarity (mean 2.98. SD 0.23), visioning (mean 3.11. SD 0.16), goal setting and planning (mean 3.06. SD 0.16). Some correlations among these dimensions ($r = 0.187$ to 0.661) suggest a hierarchy in the competency profile of action expectations that should be considered for developing programs career guidance and counseling service program that integrates the hope action theory. It is expected that programs career guidance and counseling that integrates the hope action theory will be more effective in enhancing career development.

Keywords: *Hope action theory, Adolescence, Career intervention*

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Introduction

At the end of 2019, the first case of a new variant of the virus, Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19), was discovered. By 2021, the virus had spread worldwide and caused confirmed cases to increase and even cause deaths. Based on Presidential decree of the republic of Indonesia no 11 of 2020 concerning the Determination of a Covid-10 Public Health Emergency, the virus was declared an emergency condition (Syauqi, 2020). These conditions ultimately have an impact on various sectors ranging from social and even economic society. In addition to the emergency conditions that occur, the world is currently faced with an era of technological disruption which currently results in uncertainty and various challenges that need to be faced (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). This era is characterized by the rapid development of information technology and affects various aspects of human life. One of the age levels most affected by this condition is the young age level. Research shows that young people with certain characteristics are vulnerable to unemployment (Abrar, Amalia, & Handoyo, 2019). According to data from the Ministry of Manpower as of April 20, 2020, there were 2,084,593 workers from 116,370 companies experiencing layoffs. It also caused the economy to decline, and some people lost their jobs (Kusuma & Nurchayati, 2021). This condition ultimately requires career selection competencies in the right pre-employment age profile to overcome these challenges.

However, in various existing studies, adolescents are still faced with various problems related to their ability to plan their current careers or achieve career development effectively. There are still adolescents and even students living aimlessly (Damon, 2009). This is reinforced by the results of research from (Ling, 2021) which states that at the high school level in the province of Gandong, it was found that 244 high school students reported that only 11% planned for the future and 65% did not have a clear understanding of their university and career.

These results are not much different from Indonesia, a survey conducted by UMN's (Multimedia Nusantara University) Skystar Ventures Tech Incubator startup Youthmanual (Putri, 2018) looked at approximately 400,000 profiles and data of students and college students in Indonesia, which stated that 92% of high school or vocational students still have confusion and do not know what they want to be in the future. One way that can be done is by assisting in the form of career guidance. According to (Surya, 1997) career guidance is one type of guidance that seeks to assist students in solving career problems and obtaining good self-adjustment between the environment and abilities to obtain success in their life journey. Because of that career guidance is important to be given to students. Therefore, career guidance requires the design of an appropriate program. This career development program needs to be done to help students assess personal suitability, and talents before deciding on their career exploration or orientation (Suherman, 2013) This is supported by (Ling, 2021) where almost 80% of the students opined that they wished schools could offer career guidance and wanted to know more about different universities and majors as well as various jobs and their associated requirements.

According to existing data, students who can continue to the university stage are only around 60% (Pratama, Rumangkit, Darmawan, & Mousadecq, 2023). High school graduates are forced to look for work and are faced with various competitions that are less balanced with SMK graduates. It was also explained that for those who were able to continue their education to a higher level, in this case, a bachelor's degree in February 2015, as many as 400 thousand became unemployed (Alam, 2016).

There are several important behaviors and attitudes that students need to develop to overcome career challenges that will be experienced throughout life. The development of these competencies is expected to help students overcome career challenges. One alternative that can be done in career guidance by a counseling teacher is to apply the Hope Action theory to develop students' career skills. Hope Action theory describes competencies that can be used to guide the career development process (Niles et al., 2010). The theory addresses the relatively unique career challenges of the 21st century and provides direction for understanding one's work context in a

way that effectively manages career pathways. This model is needed as an answer to the development of the current era of globalization.

This model was proposed by Niles, et al., in 2014. Since its development, the theory has become an important component of various research projects. This theory emphasizes hope as the center of the intervention provided to the counselee. (Niles, et al., 2014) state that without having hope, counsees in this case high school students will not be motivated to start the future and act. This theory is a model that can be used by counsees and professionals in career planning and maintenance activities to guide one's career planning (Niles et al., 2021). Through this method, it is hoped that the counselee will be able to have 6 abilities that make hope the main basis. Action Hope theory, previously known as the hope-centered career development model, describes competencies that can be used to guide the career development process (Niles et al., 2010).

The theory addresses the relatively unique career challenges of the 21st century and provides direction for understanding one's work context in a way that effectively manages career pathways. Career pathways refer to the difficult, demanding work and each individual's ability to navigate through situations that are either challenging, burdensome, tedious or enjoyable Niles, et al., (2011). Hope action theory uses the metaphor of a pinwheel to illustrate the centrality of action-orientated hope to the seven career competencies. Action-orientated hope to the seven career competencies. Each of the seven career competencies is useful for managing one's career path effectively Niles, et al., (2011). This theory emphasizes hope as the center of the intervention with the counsellor. Without hope, counsellors will not be motivated to start thinking about their future and take action. Niles, et al., (2014). Very few career theories touch on hope, let alone use it as a central part and cannot implicitly assume that the counsellor has hope. This theory is a theory and model that can be used by individuals and professionals during career planning and career maintenance to guide career planning Niles, et al. (2021).

The action hope theory itself offers proven and tested strategies that have been used with a wide variety of people. Strategies that have been used with a wide variety of different populations and can help guide a counsellor's career during the can help guide a counsellor's career during difficult times Niles, et al, (2021). Hope is essential for gaining momentum in individual career planning Niles, et al (2021). Niles goes further by saying that hope alone is not enough and he argues that "a critical component of career development is the that "a critical component of career development is action-orientated expectations" to ensure individuals participate and are action-orientated expectations" to ensure individuals participate and engaged in career planning activities (Niles, 2014).

This study aims to map the HAI (Hope-Action Inventory) profile of 82 high school students as the basis for career guidance and counseling service programs in high school. By looking at the profile of hope action theory, it is hoped that students will be able to develop their abilities to prepare for their future careers appropriately, and for guidance and counseling teachers this research can be initial data to provide services through a new method model as an alternative to career guidance provided, as well as other researchers who are expected to develop hope action methods which can later be further developed in various research contexts related to careers. Hope action mapping is based on research (Yoon, 2015) which suggests experimental research in conclusion. Therefore, the researcher provides an initial overview of the description of hope action in adolescents as a basis for conducting experimental research in further research to be carried out.

Method

This study aims to map the HAI (Hope-Action Inventory) profile of 82 high school students as the basis for career guidance and counseling service programs in high school. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling. According to (Sugiyono, 2013) purposive sampling technique is a data source sampling technique with certain considerations. To achieve objective from this research, various

procedure was carried out such as, (1) adapting the action hope instrument (HAI) from Niles and translating it into Indonesian by an expert. (2) conducting construct validity test on career guidance and counseling expert; (3) distributing HAI instrument; (4) testing validity and reliability using SPSS; (5) conducting analysis using SPSS.

The purposive sampling technique selects a group of subjects based on certain characteristics that are considered to have a relationship with the characteristics or characteristics of the population to be studied. The method used in this research is a descriptive study of the results of hope-action competencies. The HAI measures competencies that are important for effectively managing one's career development.

Figure 1. Stage of research

Findings and Discussion

This study found that 13,2% of students were still in the low-hope action competency category. This condition shows that there are some students have difficulty identifying future career options. Students in this case are in the stage of wondering how the current education is related to the future. Student with low hope action competency will find difficult to identify goals, especially in their career field. So that the low condition of hope action competency shows the urgency of further research that needs to be done. Students with high hope action competency, it correlates with high levels of job performance, sport performance, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, clarity in career decisions, self-confidence, and academic achievement. A book written by (Niles, et al., 2021) states that students who are in the low category this means that students, in this case, feel that the current situation about their career development is that it does not provide meaningful hope. 74.4% of students experienced challenges and positives at the same time. There are various opportunities in the current situation. Students in this category are key in making good decisions (Amundson, et al., 2020). In this case, students go through a process of increasing self-understanding, using increased self-understanding in imagining the future, then going through the process of making plans, which ultimately leads students to implement decisions that can provide an overview of information about themselves and the future and its various possibilities. There are 12.2% of students who have high hopes for their future because they find various opportunities that lead to the future. Students already feel that the environment is supportive and have found ways and strategies that can be applied.

Figure 2. Profile of Adolescents' Action Hope Competencies

Some of the dimensions of competence measured showed a range of several dimensions of Action Hope competency that were still undetermined, namely the dimensions of self-clarity (mean 2.98. SD 0.23), Vision (mean 3.11. SD 0.16), Goal setting and Planning (mean 3.06. SD 0.16). This may be due to students lack of knowledge with how increase clarity of self, purpose in life, and future goals and how to plans. This can be helped by creating a specific context and action hope-based career guidance program to develop these dimensions. Some correlations among these dimensions ($r = 0.187$ to 0.661) suggest a hierarchy in the competency profile of action expectations that should be considered for developing programs. With the results of this study, it is expected that hope action programs will be more effective in enhancing career development. Research on hope action against students in Indonesia is still relatively new. So, there are still many things that can be explored regarding the current career guidance model. After the past pandemic conditions and the challenges of global development in the present, career intervention through hope expressed in action is something that needs attention.

Figure 3. Profile of Adolescents' Action Hope Competencies

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the hope competence of students on average chose a very suitable option worth 3.22. This illustrates that students have hope which is important in managing their career development (Gelişimi & Kullanılması, 2010). Hope relates to

envisioning meaningful goals and believing positive outcomes are likely to occur if certain actions are to be taken. Snyder describes it as "the perceived ability to acquire a path toward a desired goal, and to motivate oneself through agency thinking to use that path" (1995). It can also illustrate that students who have high expectations are less likely to postpone tasks. The results of this study illustrate that hope leads students to take specific steps in achieving future goals. (Alexander & Onwuegbuzie, 2007).

The range of answer options for the self-reflection dimension is 3.34. Self-reflection is the capacity to examine thoughts, beliefs, behaviors, and circumstances. Meanwhile, the range of choices for the self-clarity dimension is 2.98. This dimension refers to how students have clear identification related to abilities, interests, values, and personality (Amundson, Goddard, Niles, Yoon, & Schidt, 2016). The range for visioning options was 3.11. Visioning focuses on brainstorming about the future and its possibilities. By having visioning, a student will focus on possibilities rather than probability thinking (Pryor, Amundson, & Bright, 2008). In the dimension of goal setting and planning, the answer choices were around 3.06. This dimension refers to the ability to consider careful steps and specific actions. The choices become more specific and the steps of the path that have been made can be implemented. In this dimension, it is important to set concrete and realistic goals. All actions are directed toward achieving goals (Amundson, Goddard, Niles, Yoon, & Schidt, 2016). In the last dimension, implementing and adapting, the answer choices ranged from 3.13 to 3.27. This dimension shows students' ability to carry out their goals to recognize that everything may not go according to what was planned. In this case, flexibility ability is needed in modifying goals and other alternatives. (Amundson, Goddard, Niles, Yoon, & Schidt, 2016).

In other studies, have revealed counselling steps and interventions that suit the unique circumstances and needs of clients in Turkey. In this study, there is a shortcoming that the sample described is only 1 person, so the comparison intervention still cannot be clearly described. Niles, S. G., Yoon, H. J., Balin, E., & Amudson, N.A (2010). Whereas the previous article focused on a case study, this study conducted an experiment. The weaknesses in this study are related to the validity of the measurement tools and their usefulness. Yoon, H. J., Bailey, N., Amundson, N., & Niles, S. (2019). Weaknesses in other studies were found relating to the effectiveness of the HAI when using psychometrics and interventions in similarly situated samples. Amundson, N., Niles, S. G., & Yoon, H. J. (2020). Other studies have shown that the HAI has strong predictive validity for education. The results of this study showed that there were significant group differences among different employment status and age groups. The weakness of this study is the limited sample where validation activities are carried out on most people of European descent. So, there is still a need for validation of measuring instruments that are adapted to countries that will conduct research related to HAI (Currie, 2020).

The development of hope action interventions especially student hope needs to be concern, because if student have low hope, then student will be low academic achievement, low student engagement, and vocational identity. Yoon, et al., (2015). Hope is a crucial factor that influences various aspects of a student life. It is a key focus and objective in human existence, central to many activities. Student with high levels of hope have clear direction and purpose, leading them to preform good deeds. Developing hope significantly impacts academic achievement, drop out rates, mental health, and physical health Asiah et al., (2022). Therefore, the objective of this article is describing profile hope action competency that has been tested from student. The result showed that interventions are needed to develop action hope competencies that are underdeveloped.

Action hope theory uses the metaphor of a pinwheel to illustrate the centrality of action-orientated hope to the seven career competencies. Each of the seven career competencies is useful for effectively managing one's career path Niles (2011). This theory emphasizes hope as central to the intervention with the counsellor. Without hope, counsellors will not be motivated to start thinking about their future and take action. Niles et al., (2014). Very few careers' theories touch on hope, let alone use it as a central part and cannot implicitly assume that the counselee has hope.

It is a theory and model that can be used by individuals and professionals during career planning and maintenance activities to guide career planning Niles, et al., (2021). The action hope theory itself offers proven and tested strategies that have been used with a variety of different populations and can help guide a counsellor's career during difficult times Niles, et al. (2021).

Hope is essential for gaining momentum in an individual's career planning Niles, et al (2021). Niles goes so far as to say that hope alone is not enough and she argues that "a critical component of career development is action-orientated hope" to ensure individuals participate and engage in career planning activities (Niles, 2014, p. 1). One of the steps to shape the integration of action hope theory into career development practice, Yoon (2018) suggests six steps, namely (1) match current interventions with each element of action hope theory; (2) identify areas of strength and challenge for each element of action hope theory; (3) develop additional interventions and extend existing interventions to other areas; (4) integrate and streamline the interventions offered, making them aligned with each other using action hope theory as a framework; (5) build a new system that allows to deliver more value with the same level of effort; (6) evaluate the effectiveness of the new system.

In the Future researchers, it can develop research related to action hope with more comprehensive methods, so that not only profile the level of student abilities but it is hoped that it can provide an appropriate intervention to develop students' abilities. In addition, the factors that influence such as career planning need to be studied more deeply and fully presented with specific factors that greatly affect students' abilities.

Some research on HAI still focuses on special samples such as drug abuse patients, unemployment, students at universities. So that the application of HAI to high school students can be categorized as not too much has been done. (Dixson, 2019). In addition, based on previous research, the use of HAI is limited to samples with certain cultures, so there needs to be adjustments related to the use of sample categorization. If applied in Indonesia, HAI must be done carefully considering that previous research has never been done in this country. This can be anticipated by future researchers. In terms of methods, some studies focused on longitudinal and interviews and case studies as well as in the context of face-to-face personal counselling services. Therefore, future research can use experimental methods by testing career guidance services based on HAI that have implications for students' career planning in senior high schools.

Conclusion

There are still students hope action abilities that are in the low category, therefore there is a need for efforts from guidance and counseling teachers to improve these abilities through interventions in the form of models or programs that are planned and systematic to improve these abilities by placing hope as the core of career services in schools to prepare students for the development of the current era of disruption. Based on these findings, it can be seen that the ability that needs to be developed is self-clarity, vision, goal setting and planning. One form of intervention that can be done further is to create a model of developing action hope competencies by creating a development module for each competency so that career development can be achieved by adolescents. Although various other competencies are already in the good category, maintaining exactly this competency needs to be considered more carefully.

Future research is also expected to develop better by adding variables related to career either educational settings, or even the situation of samples who are in the stage of having no hope of achieving something.

References

- Abrar, M., Amalia, N., & Handoyo, R. D. (2019). Karakteristik dan Peluang Peagngguran Usia Muda di Provinsi Aceh Dalam Menghadapi Era Revolusi Industri 4.0. *Jurnal Kebijakan Pembangunan*, 14(20), 157-169.

- Alam, S. (2016). Tingkat Pendidikan dan Pengangguran di Indonesia (Telaah Serapan Tenaga Kerja SMA/SMK dan Sarjana). *Jurnal Imiah BONGAYA (Manajemen & Akuntansi)*, No.XIX.
- Alexander, & Onwuegbuzie. (2007). Academic procrastination and the role of hope as a coping strategy. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 1301-1310.
- Amundson, Goddard, Niles, Yoon, & Schidt. (2016). Hope Centered Career Intervention. <https://ceric.ca/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/Hope-Project-Final-Report.pdf>.
- Amundson, N., Niles, S., & Yoon, H. J. (2020). Kulturowe I Spoleczne Konteksty Wychowania. *Psychologia Wychowania*, DOI:10.560401.3001.0014.6277.
- Asiah, Rusmana, & Saripah (2022). Strength-Based Counseling: Alternative Counseling to Increase Student Hope During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Bisma The Journal of Counseling* 6(1):1-7. DOI:[10.23887/bisma.v6i1.45347](https://doi.org/10.23887/bisma.v6i1.45347)
- Currie (2020). Factor structure of the hope-action-inventory in a problematic substance use sample. The University of British Columbia
- Damon. (2009). *The Path to Purpose Helping Our Children Find Their Calling in Life*. America: Free Press
- Dixson, D. D. (2019). Hope into action: How clusters of hope relate to success-oriented behavior in school. *Wiley*, DOI: 10.1002/pits.22299.
- Gelişimi, Z. Z., & Kullanılması, M. (2010). Using A Hope-Centered Model of Career Development in Challenging Times. *Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Journal*, 4 (34), 101-108.
- Kusuma, T., & Nurchayati. (2021). Sikap Dan Perilaku Masyarakat Terhadap Pandemi Covid-19. *Ejournal Unesa*.
- Ling. (2021). An Analysis Report of the Survey of the High School Student's Career Planning in Guangdong Province After College Entrance Examination Reformation. *Mental Health education in primary and secondary school*, 1(1), pp.21–24 (in Chinese).
- Niles, S., Amundson, N., Neaut, R., & Yoon, H. J. (2021). *Career Flow & Development Hope in Action Second Edition*. United States of America: Cognella Academic Publishing.
- Niles, et.al., (2014). Using an Action Oriented Hope-Centered Model of Career Development. *Journal of Asia Pacific Counseling*, Vol.4, No.1, 1-13 Doi: 10.18401/2014.4.1.1.
- Niles, et.al., (2011). *Career Flow; A hope-centered approach to career development*. Pearson Education
- Niles, S., Yoon, H. J., Bahn, E., & Amundson, N. (2010). Using A Hope Center Model of Career Development in Challenging Times. *Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Journal*, 4(34).
- Putri, N. (2018) *Youthmanual: Angka siswa yang salah pilih jurusan masih tinggi*. Skystar Ventures. Universitas Multimedia Nusantara.
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A Literature Review on Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. *Sage Journals Higher Education for the Future*, Volume 8, Issue 1 <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631120983481>.
- Pratama, Y. A., Rumangkit, S., Darmawan, A., & Mousadecq, A. (2023). Faktor yang memengaruhi calon mahasiswa dalam memilih perguruan tinggi di provinsi lampung. *Jurnal Humanipreneur*, Volume 2 No 1.
- Pryor, R., Amundson, N., & Bright, J. (2008). Probabilities and possibilities: The strategic counseling implications of the chaos theory of careers. *The Career Development Quarterly*, 56,309-318.

- Snyder, C. R. (1995). Conceptualizing, measuring, and nurturing hope. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 73(3), 355-360. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1556-6676.1995.tb01764.x>
- Suherman, U. (2013). *Bimbingan dan Konseling Karir Sepanjang Rentang Kehidupan*. Bandung: Sekolah Pascasarjana UPI.
- Surya, M. (1997). *Bimbingan untuk Mempersiapkan Generasi Muda*. Bandung: Pidato Pengukuhan Guru Besar.
- Sugiyono. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R & D*. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Syauqi, A. (2020). Jalan Panjang Covid 19 (sebuah refleksi dikala wabah merajalela berdampak pada perekonomian). *Jurnal Keuangan dan Perbankan Syariah*, JKUBS, 1(1), 1-19. Retrieved from <https://e-journal.iainptk.ac.id/index.php/jkubs/article/view/115>.
- Yoon, H.J. (2018). Understanding and applying Hope-Action Theory [희망-실천 이론의 이해와 적용]. *Career Info*, 13, 14– 23. [In Korean].
- Yoon, Bailey, Admundson, & Niles. (2019). The effect of a career development programme based on the hope-action hope theory: Hope to Work for refugees in British Columbia. *British Journal of Guidance and Counseling*, 47(1), 6-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03069885.2018.1544827>.
- Yoon, H. J., Hyoyeon, Niles, S., & Amundson, N. (2015). The Effects of Hope on Student Engagement, Academic Performance, and Vocational Identity. *Canadian Journal of Career Development*, Vol 14 No 1.